

THE ROLE OF THE MAHALAN IN INCREASING THE SOCIO-POLITICAL ACTIVITY OF WOMEN

Sagdullayeava Dilnoza Shukhratovna

Bagishamol MFY women's activist, Khatirchi district,
Navoi region, Republic of Uzbekistan

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Abstract: The development of the reforms implemented in our republic depends in many ways on the spiritual image and personal integrity of the youth. The implementation of these tasks requires a deep reflection of democratic principles in human relations.

In our developing country, great attention is paid to raising a healthy generation and perfect people. Increasing the socio-political activity of young people is one of the most urgent problems today. In addition, based on the concept of "legal culture", it is possible to approach political activity as a political-legal feature specific to young people.

Keywords: communication, language, neighborhood, mind, speech, perception, need, behavior, information, personality, communication, communication

The development of reforms implemented in our republic depends in many ways on the spiritual image and personal perfection of young people. The implementation of these tasks requires deep thinking of democratic principles in human relations.

In our developing country, great attention is paid to women in raising a healthy generation and perfect people. Increasing the socio-political activity of women is one of the most urgent problems today. In addition, based on the concept of "legal culture", it is possible to approach political activity as a political-legal feature specific to women.

Also, the content of the process of formation of women's political and legal activism includes the following:

- 1) knowledge of law;
- 2) attitude to law;
- 3) targeting based on legal behavior;
- 4) realizing the necessity of one's legal behavior;+

Women are the most necessary and rapidly changing potential of the country's population in social life, a layer close to each other in terms of its structure. attention is increasing significantly.

In order to bring up a fully developed, mature, perfect person (person), it is necessary to bring up young people to think freely. Therefore, communication is formed in an integral connection with thinking.

There are ideas that are intended to be implemented in the future in our country, and they are performing the function of a perspective program that determines the development of our country. These ideas are:

- 1) The future of Uzbekistan is a great country
- 2) enlightening the minds of citizens with the torch of spirituality
- 3) Building a democratic, legal, civil society in Uzbekistan
- 4) education of independent thinking, active, dedicated people
- 5) is like perfecting a perfect person.

The national idea of our country is common to all nations. The national idea ensures that the religious faith of the youth, a prosperous life, loyalty to the sense of mutual harmony, independence, and dreams come true. And the youth who are considered the future of the country women educate. A healthy woman gives birth to a healthy child. Our women with spiritual and legal knowledge will bring up the young generation needed for the future.

Currently, in our country, attention is paid to the neighborhood system, and efforts are being made to support women in all aspects and involve them in entrepreneurship.

According to the relevant decree of the President, from the 2022/2023 academic year:

1.8 trillion soums are allocated annually from the budget to banks to provide 7-year interest-free loans to pay the contracts of women studying in higher education institutions, technical institutes and colleges, part-time and evening education;

the contract fees of all women studying for master's degrees in public higher education institutions will be covered, and at least 200 billion soums will be allocated for this every year;

50 women for bachelor's degree and 10 women for master's degree are allocated additional grants to foreign higher education institutions every year through the "El-Yurt Umid" fund;

every year, the education contracts of 2,100 socially needy family members, orphans or students who are deprived of their parents' care are paid from the local budget;

500 women who have at least 5 years of work experience in their specialty, but do not have a higher education, take special tests every year, in addition to the

general quota, to state higher education institutions based on the recommendations of the State Committee for Family and Women according to the results, he is admitted to study on the basis of a contract;

a targeted quota of at least 300 is allocated annually for women to doctoral studies in state scientific organizations or higher educational institutions.

In Uzbekistan, within the framework of "National goals and tasks in the field of sustainable development until 2030", one of the priority goals is "Ensuring gender equality and expanding the rights and opportunities of all women".

Ushbu maqsadga erishish uchun xotin-qizlarning o'z huquq va manfaatlarini ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy sohada amalga oshirishida ularni qo'llab-quvvatlashni nazarda tutuvchi dasturlarni kengaytirish talab etiladi.

In 2022 - 2026, the National Program for increasing the activity of women in all aspects of the country's economic, political and social life (hereinafter referred to as the National Program) outlines the main directions of the state policy for supporting women. defines.

The national program is the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, "On State Policy Regarding Youth", "On Protection of Women from Harassment and Violence", "Guarantees of Equal Rights and Opportunities for Women and Men" on" the laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the decision of the Senate of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On approval of the strategy for achieving gender equality in the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030", generally recognized principles and norms of international law , prepared in accordance with the provisions of the international agreements of the Republic of Uzbekistan and other legal documents.

The national program considers women's rights as an integral part of human rights, and it is a set of measures for comprehensive support of women based on the principle of "For human dignity".

The development and implementation of the national program serves as an important factor in creating the necessary conditions for the full participation of women in the political, economic, social and cultural life of society on the basis of equal rights.

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